

NATIONAL DRUGS LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCY ON ABUSE OF DRUGS AMONG YOUTHS IN UYO METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

Drugs abuse is a serious societal issue both nationally and internationally due to its high prevalence. Nigeria continues to have a high rate of drugs abuse among youths. Drugs abuse is the Illegal use of substances that change a person's mental state and that destroy his/her life. Some drugs misused include alcohol, marijuana, opium, heroin, cocaine etc. The purpose of the study is to investigate the roles of NDLEA, the factors that lead to youths drugs abuse in Uyo metropolis, analyse how drugs addiction affects social instability, and examine how families and the local community might help prevent youths drugs abuse. The study adopted a qualitative research design to guarantee a thorough analysis of the data, with the used of simple random sampling technique. This required conducting in-depth interviews with 40 interviewees, whose answers were then classified into themes according to study's goals. Using an interview schedule, a semi-structured face-to-face interview was employed. Based on the study's findings, drug abuse and insecurity are significantly correlated. The findings indicate that the availability of drugs in the country, peer group influence, despair, unemployment, failure of parental control over children and drugs misuse are some of the factors that contribute to drugs abuse. Drugs have negative social, financial and health implications. The study recommends among others, that family and community member should disseminate information about the dangers of drugs, monitor and supervise children's activities with their peer group, working with professionals to address drugs abuse among our youths, identify and address risk factors associated with drugs abuse and empower youths to take an active role in preventing drugs abuse. And more so, foster collaboration and coordination among government agencies, non-governmental organizations, healthcare providers, educational institutions, law enforcement agencies, and community members to address drugs abuse comprehensively.

KEYWORDS: Drug Abuse, Youth, Uyo Metropolis, Poverty, and Social Insecurity.

INTRODUCTION

Drug abuse among youths is a multifaceted phenomenon influenced by a complex interplay of individual, social, economic, and environmental factors. Culture play great role in the youths' behaviours toward drug abuse (Peters, 2019). The allure of substances such as cannabis, opioids, stimulants, and synthetic drugs poses significant risks to the physical and mental well-being of young people. Moreover, drugs abuse often leads to detrimental outcomes, including addiction, impaired cognitive function, mental health disorders, academic under achievement, delinquency, and increased and susceptibility to criminal activities. According to Effiong, Mboho, and Wordu (2018) viewed that Nigeria is one of the developing countries in Africa has on a daily basis been besieged with news of young men and women arrested in an attempt to traffic hard drugs such as cocaine, heroin and cannabis both within and outside the shores of the country. The origin of Nigeria's drug trafficking problem can be traced to the period just after the Second World War. Nigerian soldiers who had served in Burma, India, came back with seeds of the cannabis sativa plant. They went ahead to experiment with its cultivation and discovered that the plant does very well in some parts of Nigeria, and this led to a rise in the cultivation of the plant (Chr. 2010). The cultivation became a national phenomenon which has exposed people to what is called drugs trafficking. A lot of Nigerian youths have taking to combining the plant with other psychoactive substances for an abuse (Peters, Bassey, Usoro, and Samuel, 2022)

Recently, there has been a proliferation of drugs and psychoactive substance use among youths in Nigeria (Peters, Usoro, James, Emeh. and Oyebanji, 2023). More disturbing is that there is a geometric rise of substance use among females. According to a documentary report by the British Broadcasting Corporation, The Cable Newspaper, about three million bottles of codeine is consumed in Nigeria daily, and out of this, more than half of the total bottles are consumed in Kano and Jigawa alone, mostly by females. This is in addition to a widespread abuse of drugs such as tramadol, cannabis, and other psychoactive substances that have dire consequences on the physical, social, economic, and security lives of Nigerians. This day Newspaper reported that 40% of Nigerian youths engage in substance and drug abuse. To buttress the above statistic, results released by NOI Polls Limited reveal that almost 9 in 10 Nigerians (90%) believe the highest abusers of drugs and substance are teenagers and young adults aged between 15 and 29 years old. Furthermore, results show that the most abused substance in Nigeria is marijuana, codeine and alcohol, the result also reported that the key causes for the rise in drugs and substance abuse are poverty and unemployment (Peter, Usoro, Mboho, and Ononokpono, 2023).

By far the most commonly abused and misused drugs by youths in Nigeria are Tramadol and Codeine. Tramadol is a synthetic opioid analgesic used to treat moderate and severe pains. According Wilson, Usoroh, and Peters (2020), this misused of tramadol is the unorthodox use of orthodox drugs among youths. In prescribed doses it has no negative effects on the respiratory system but an overdose causes arrhythmias, cramps, coma and eventually death. Codeine on the other hand is commonly prescribed as a painkiller because it is relatively mild when compared with any other opioid painkillers. It is nevertheless dangerous and could easily lead to dependence. Prolonged and frequent Codeine abused can lead to maladaptive behaviours and health problems, including death. The effect of drugs on individuals and the society at large cannot be over emphasized. Drug addiction and substance abuse can be linked

to various ill effects in the society. Several findings as shown that substance abuse to a large extent is directly related to the increase in crime and violence in the country. A number of abusers, especially youths and young adults, have been identified to be involved in armed robbery and daring exploits (Peters *et al.*, 2023). Peters and Bassey (2020) have discovered drug abuse as a way of live among some of the youths in the riverine area. Among the young farmers in farm settlement areas, Peters, Bassey, and Nya, (2020) reported that abuse of drugs is based on the nature of works within the area. Substance abuse has also been linked, to a certain level, to early school dropout and a number of HIV/AIDS cases due to the sharing of needles in the course of administrating drugs

The abuse of drugs among youths is a pressing concern globally, with significant implications for public health, social well-being, and economic development. Within Nigeria, this issue is particularly acute, with various regions grappling with the adverse effects of drugs abuse among their youth populations. In recent years, the Uyo metropolis has witnessed a troubling rise in the prevalence of drugs abuse among its youth population. This trend not only jeopardizes the health and future prospects of individuals but also undermines the-social fabric and economic vitality of the community. Addressing this issue requires a comprehensive understanding of the root causes, dynamics, and consequences of drugs abuse within the local context. On this backdrop, this study investigate the roles of National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency on abuse of drugs among youths in Uyo Metropolis.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The researcher sought to answer the following question as dependent on the objective of the study:

1. What is the prevalence rate of drugs abuse among youths (aged 15-35) in the Uyo metropolis?
2. What are the socio-demographic profiles (e.g., age, gender, education, marital status, employment status) of individuals engaged in drugs abuse within the Uyo metropolis?
3. What are the causes of drugs abuse among youths in Uyo metropolis?
4. How does drug abuse affect social insecurity in Uyo Metropolis?
5. What are the roles of enforcement agencies, family and community members in curtailing drug abuse among youths?

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF TERMS

Drug Abuse: Drug abuse refers to the habitual or excessive use of psychoactive substances, including both illicit drugs (such as cocaine, heroin, and methamphetamine) and legal substances (such as alcohol and prescription medications), leading to negative consequences for the individual's health, social functioning, or well-being. (Mboho, and Udoh, 2018).

Youths: For the purpose of this study, youths refer to individuals within the age range of 15 to 35 years old. This demographic group is often characterized by developmental transitions from adolescence to adulthood and is particularly vulnerable to peer influences, societal pressures, und risk-taking behaviours, including drugs abuse (Mboho, 2021).

Prevalence: Prevalence refers to the proportion of individuals in a population who exhibit a particular characteristic or behaviour at a specific point in time or over a defined period. In the content of this study, prevalence specifically relates to the frequency or rate of drugs abuse

among youths in Uyo metropolis.

Socio-Demographic Characteristics: Socio-demographic characteristics encompass various attributes of individuals related to their social and demographic us. This includes factors such as age, gender, education level, marital status, employment status, income level, and household composition. Understanding these characteristics can provide insights into the demographic profiles of drug abusers in Uyo metropolis (Mboho, and Udo, 2013).

Severity of Drug Abuse: Severity of drugs abuse refers to the extent on intensity of the negative consequences associated with substance misused or dependence. This can compass various dimensions, including physical health, mental well-being, social functioning academic or occupational performance, legal issues, and interpersonal relationships.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Assessing the National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA)

The National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) is a Federal agency in Nigeria charged with eliminating the growing, processing, manufacturing, selling, exporting, and trafficking of hard drugs. According to Obot, (2023) the agency was established in 1989 as a response to the United Nations Convention against illicit Trafficking in Narcotics Drugs and Psychotropic Substances of 1988. Among many of its provisions, the NDLEA Decree set up an agency of the same name and hated the punishment for drug offences, including the forfeiture of assets of arrested persons. In this Decree, trafficking in cocaine, LSD, heroin, or similar drugs is punishable by life imprisonment, while possession or use attracts a sentence of '15 years but not exceeding 25 years'. Since the agency was established, it has put in spirited efforts in the enforcement of laws on drugs trafficking and abuse. To this effect, so many persons have been prosecuted, and sent to prison with varying jail terms consignments of drugs and substances confirmed to be prohibited or counterfeits worth billions of naira are destroyed from time to time, and articles, vehicles and vessels used by drug law breakers are confiscated by the agency.

However, Obot, (2023) observed that even after the establishment of the agency in 1989, drug trafficking continued unabated in the 1990s leading to the decertification of Nigeria by the United States of America in 1994. The beginning of Nigeria's status as a pariah nation for five years was the announcement of U.S. certification decisions for 1993 that were made in early 1994. The country was decertified for failing on its drug control efforts and severe sanctions were imposed. The only other countries to be decertified that year were Myanmar, Iran, and Syria. It was a difficult company to keep and probably much more so when Afghanistan was added to the list of decertified nations the following year. The criteria for determining drug transit status are not as concrete. A country falls on the majors list if it is 'a significant direct source of illicit narcotic or psychotropic drugs or other controlled substances significantly affecting the United State; or through which are transported such drugs or substances' to the U.S. (Bureau of International Narcotics and Law Enforcement Affairs cited in Obot, 2003).

Willie, Mboho, and Oyosoro (2022) observes that the structural setup and orientation of the agency as a law enforcement institution has made it difficult for it to professionally handle drug use as a public health issue. The institution is situated under the Ministry of Justice. Hence there is a natural default towards the use of criminal sanctions in its operation. A

look at the agency's mission statement, which uses the word "suppression of Demand for illicit drugs and other substance of abuse, is a pointer to the use of force even for a response that should be health centered.

According to Obot, (2003) the NDLEA had become "Nigeria's stinking house of drugs and there were regular stories in the media about scandals at the agency. The agency over the years has been involved in various scandals that have affected its operation including corruption, collecting gratification from drug traffickers, pilfering of seized drugs, military interference in the agency, and poor funding among others. The issue of corruption and collection of gratification from drugs started from the inception of the agency in 1990. The first chairman of the agency, Mr. Fidelis Oyakhilome, a Commissioner of Police, was butted out of office due to corruption allegations that were leveled on him.

According to Uwiagbo (n.d.), (2018) in January 1993, a senior officer of the agency was suspended for allegedly masterminding the removal of 200 grams of cocaine exhibits expelled from the bowels of a detained suspected drug courier. In February 1993, the nation was stunned with the disappearance of 40 tons of Indian Hemp impounded earlier during a raid in Ondo State. The weed was valued at N1.5 million. In May 1993, an Assistant Director of the Agency was sentenced to 10 years imprisonment for receiving a bribe of N100,000. In November 1993 massive corrupt practices were reported in Kano Zonal Command of the NDLEA. Udoh, Mboho, and Umo, (2020) reported that there were sloppy handling of exhibits, missing equipment donated by the international community, improper use of machines and dogs, vandalism of drug detecting equipment, conflicts between the agency and other law enforcement bodies over the handling of cases, loss of case files, low morale and corruption among agents which are attributed to poor conditions of service and increasing murder of agents by suspected traffickers and cannabis farmers.

Rundown of Drug Policies in Nigeria

There is dearth of information on drug policy in Nigeria during the early era of colonisation up to 1914 when the country was birthed. However, the first known law against drugs abuse and trafficking in Nigeria is the Dangerous Drugs Ordinance of 1935. According to Nwannennaya & Abiodun, (2017) the Dangerous Drugs Ordinance guided the then Board of Customs and Excise and the Nigerian Police under the colonial government to tackle drugs abuse and trafficking locally. Thereafter, the Indian hemp [Cannabis] Decree of 1966 was promulgated by the military government of General J.T.U. Aguiyi Ironsi, now in an independent, Nigeria. Under this Decree, cultivation of cannabis attracted the death penalty or 21 years in jail, and exportation was punishable by 10 years of imprisonment. Also under the decree, a stiff penalty of at least 10 years in jail was reserved for those found smoking or in possession of the drugs, Federal Military Government (1966).

According to Obot, (2003) the Indian Hemp Decree of 1966 was amended in 1975 and the punitive provisions were made less severe. Hence, the amendment expunged the death penalty for the cultivation of cannabis, while the punishment for cannabis smoking was lessened to six months and/or a fine (Federal Military Government (1975) cited in Obot. However, in 1984 the military government of Buhari/Idiagbon changed the punitive provisions of the Indian Hemp Decree of 1966 (Amended) by re-introducing the death penalty which the original decree stipulated. Also under the repealed law, any person under the age of 17 years was to be given 21 strokes of the cane, 2 years in borstal or fine of N200.00 for smoking or possession.

According to Ogege, (2010) a special Tribunal (Miscellaneous Offences) Decree came up in the later part of 1981. The decree abolished death penalty on drugs abuse due to public outcry which greeted it. However, the decree instituted life imprisonment for importing, manufacturing. Producing, processing, planting or growing of cocaine, Cannabis, Lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD), heroin or other narcotic drugs, imprisonment not exceeding 20 years for exporting, transporting or trafficking. A jail term of not less than 14 years for selling, buying, exposing for sale or dealing was instituted, imprisonment of not less than 3 years (but not more than 10 years) for possession or consumption. Forfeiture of assets and passports was also instituted and a special tribunal was set up solely for the enforcement of drug laws. In 1986, with the coming of a new military government of General Ibrahim Babangida, the 1984 Decree was amended and life imprisonment was substituted for the death penalty. This Special Tribunal (Miscellaneous Offences) (Amendment) Decree of 1986 introduced new features into Nigerian drug law, the most significant of which was the provision regarding forfeiture of assets and passport (Obot, 2003).

In 1989, following a disturbing increase in drug trafficking in Nigeria, the Decree 48 of 1989 was enacted leading to the establishment of the National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA). This is regarded as the most significant drug control policy in Nigeria. The agency's primary mandate was to tackle the menace of drugs abuse and trafficking which was spoiling the image of the country at that time as the United States Government was beginning to express its unhappiness with the Nigerian Government because of the growing role of Nigerians in exacerbating the drug problem in the US. Obot reported that not only were Nigerians fringing drugs into the US, those resident in the country and in Asia were using inner-city gangs to distribute drugs in urban neighbourhoods (Peter, Usoro, Mboho, and Ononokpono, 2023).

Another notable drugs control policy in Nigeria was in 1995 with the promulgation of the Money Laundering Decree No. 3 by the military government of General Sani Abacha which gave greater powers to the NDLEA to mount surveillance on the bank accounts of suspects. The Decree also placed limitations on cash payments, mandated banks to report deposits of amounts beyond a certain limit and gave powers to the NDLEA to tap any telephone line [10]. Also, recently, following a spiral increase in the abuse of drugs by the youths especially in the North, two committees on the eradication of drugs abuse headed by Buba Marwa and Boss Mustapha were set up by the Buhari government in December 2018. It is left to know what the outcome from these committees will be. But Nigeria is far from achieving a drug free society at the moment, (Mboho, and Tahiri, 2014).

NDLEA embarks on awareness programmes

Public awareness campaigns is one powerful tool drug fighting agencies use all over the world to campaign against drugs abuse, illicit drug trafficking and the attendant consequences. In Nigeria, the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency is charged with the responsibility of fighting drug crimes and creating awareness on drug related issues. To ensure efficiency in its awareness programmes, the NDLEA has a unit called the Drug Abuse Preventive Education (DAPE) (Okorie, Mboho, Asangausung, and Ekposon, 2021). According to NDLEA (2014), the duty of this unit is to sensitize and create awareness to the general populace on the dangers inherent in drugs abuse and illicit drug trafficking in the

society. NDLEA reported that in 2014 they delivered many public lectures nationwide especially in Secondary Schools in order to catch them young. Awareness and Sensitization Programmes were carried out in Churches, Mosques, Market places, Workplaces and out of School youth groups. A lecture was delivered for the executive members of the Lagos State Market Men and Women Association. Community Based Programmes were also organised in collaboration with non-governmental organizations. According to Ude-Akpeh (2017), NDLEA has been consistent in providing relevant information, showing the devastating consequences of drug abuse. It uses various approaches to combat the menace of drugs abuse and drug trafficking. According to Oraka, as cited in Ude-Akpeh (2017) public relation techniques is one of such approaches which the agency has adopted to deal with anti-drug campaign in Nigeria. The NDLEA in Anambra state has been up to the task in its awareness programmes in the communities and secondary schools in Anambra State. For example in 2018 the NILEA with the first lady her Excellency Mrs. Ebere Obiano the wife of the Executive Governor of Anambra State toured the 181 communities in the state on sensitization campaign against drugs abuse and drug trafficking. NDLEA, also runs a phone-in programme titled "NDLEA and you" across different radio stations in the states (ABS, UNIZIK FM and WAZOBIA FM) where they enlightened the general public on the danger of drug trafficking among other things. The NDLEA have equally established drug free clubs in the 256 Public Secondary Schools in Anambra state, where students are educated on issues relating to drugs abuse, its effects and consequences through lectures, drama and peer group counseling. They equally conducted seminar for teachers in Anambra State. Two teachers from each school took part in the seminar (Thompson Chinwe principal officer drug demand reduction unit, Personal communication September 17, 2018).

Furthermore, according to NDLEA (2017), the agency sensitized and created awareness programme to the general populace on the dangers inherent in drugs abuse and illicit trafficking in the society. They carried intensive anti-drug abuse education/awareness programmes in schools and community based programmes like churches, mosques, market and work places. The NDLEA went on to report that in 2017, the total number of programmes conducted for youths in school was 241 with 553,025 as participants. For community based 41 programmes were conducted with 14,995 as participants. Two (2) other programmes were carried out for prison inmates with 403 inmates in attendance. In the work place 32 programmes were conducted with 6,533 participants, paramilitary recorded 7 programmes with 201 personnel in attendance. Awareness programmes were also carried out in market places and 41 programmes were conducted for the media (Mboho, and Atairet, 2018).

Trend of Drugs Abuse in Nigeria

It is possible that the same drugs that are good for humanity will also be bad for humankind goes without saying that drugs are made to treat illnesses and improve the human condition, yet people may abuse over-the-counter medications, which is referred to as drugs abuse. It has affected the family, the economy, and the community, making it a social issue. Drugs abuse among youths has become a serious public health concern in our country. Following independence from Britain in the year 1960s, Nigeria observed an epidemic of drug use (Pela & Ebie, 2012). Tobacco, kola nut, and alcohol were the only narcotics that were commonly utilized during that time. Nowadays, many young people turn into anything, including alcohol drinking, tobacco smoking, and illegal use narcotics, which are the items

that are most readily available to them (Yunusa et al, 2017). The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), which was established by Decree No. 48 in 1989 to address problems related to the abusive behaviour and trafficking of narcotic drugs and other psychotropic substances other than food that, by their chemical nature, affect the structure and function of living organisms, was created as a result of this and other circumstances (Ju & Odejide, 2013; as cited in Aminu et al, 2023)

The use of drugs has been justified for several reasons. According to Ibrahim et al. (2016) and Gureje & Olley (2012), people use psychoactive drugs for a variety of reasons, including: (1) to belong to a class or social group (2) peer group pressure; (3) due to various levels of family deprivation; (4) for fun, (5) to conquer illness, (6) to build confidence; (7) to confront shyness; (8) to be capable of facilitating communication; (9) to combat many other social problems; and (10) to persuade them to work beyond their physical capability.

A dangerous drug ordinance was passed in Nigeria in 1985 to combat trafficking and abuse. This was the beginning of the country's drug control initiative (Essien, 2010). In an effort to prohibit drug trafficking within Nigerian borders, the Federal Military Government adopted the special tribunal (miscellaneous offences) Decree No. 20 of 1984 in 1994. This is due to the growing public awareness of a drug threat (Johnson, 2002). The following medications were and abused in Nigeria, according to NAFDAC (2000). They include tranquilizers, stimulants, hallucinogens, sedatives, and other substances.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Rational Choice Theory

This study is premised on the Rational Choice Theory also known as the Rational Action Theory which stipulates that an individual has preferences among available choice alternatives that allow them to state which option they prefer. This theory sufficiently explains why people always disobey drug control laws. According to Ogege, (2010) the Rational Choice Theory is a variant of the symbolic interactionist perspective which is anchored on the premise that human actions are guided by the meanings they assign to such actions. Based on the assumption people faced with several courses of action, will usually do what they believe is likely to have the best overall outcome, Elster 1989 cited in Ogege, (2010). He observed that the Rational Choice Theory explains that deviant behaviour occurs when a person weighs the costs and benefits of non-conventional or criminal behaviour and determines that the benefits will outweigh the risks involved in such actions. In other words, the theory has it that. people who commit crimes do not engage in random acts of antisocial behaviour. Instead, they make careful decisions based on weighing the available information regarding situational factors such as the place of crime, suitable targets and availability of people to deter the behaviour and personal factors such as the reward of the behaviour, Siegel (1998) cited in Ogege, (2010).

Applying the Rational Choice Theory to the breaking of drug prohibition laws, those who break the laws make rational choice by carefully calculating and weighing what they stand to gain if they embark on the manufacture, importation, sale and consumption of prohibited drugs. It is when they place the benefits side by side with the risks of being caught by Drug Law Enforcement Agents before they embark on it. The benefits could be monetary reward or psychological satisfaction (Mboho, and Ataire, 2018).

Psychological Theory

This theory suggests that drugs abuse is related to underlying psychological issues, such as low self-esteem, depression, and anxiety. Similarly, psychological theories emphasize the role of individual characteristics and experiences in drugs abuse. They explore how personality traits, psychological disorders, stress, and coping mechanisms contribute to substance abuse. For example, the self-medication theory suggests that individuals may use drugs to alleviate symptoms of mental health conditions (Khantzian, 1997)

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METHODOLOGY

Face-to-face interviews were conducted with the interviewees from each of the eleven political wards in Uyo Local Government Area of the State. These wards comprises of Uyo Urban I, Uyo Urban II, Uyo Urban III, Etoi Ward I, Etoi Ward II, Offot Ward I, Offot Ward II, Ikono ward I, Ikono Ward II, Oku Ward I, and Oku Ward II. These wards are part of the Uyo Metropolis and constitute the majority of drug addicts in the state. In order to coordinate the interviewees for the interview and translate their opinion from native tongue (Ibibio) to English, the researchers used the help of research assistants. As the most appropriate approach for this study, the paper used a qualitative research design since it depends on people's knowledge, understandings, opinions, interpretations, experiences, and interactions. In order to enhance the collection of thorough and top-notch data necessary for the study's success, the study was also designed flexible.

The researcher used the interviewing technique to get information from the interviewees. Thus, in-depth interviews are thought to be the most effective way to characterize and comprehend interviewees' perspectives on the roles of NDLEA, causes and effects of youth drug abuse as well as how drug addiction affects social insecurity. According to Zonabend (1992) the interview must be utilized to convey context and meaning. Their defense of the interview as a crucial qualitative technique is relevant to the present investigation. Using an interview schedule supplied by Sekaran (2010), where the topic and questions are disclosed in advance before the actual interview sessions take place, semi-structured face-to-face interviews were carried out for this study.

For the study, a sample of twenty interviewees was selected. They were chosen at random from among several groups of youths in Uyo Metropolis. Therefore, the simple random sampling technique was employed. These decisions were justified by an investigation of the roles of NDLEA, causes, effects, and social implications of drug abuse among youths. There was not enough time or money for a greater sample size. Male and female young people of both sexes make up the interviewees. Thematic analysis was used to interpret the data that had been gathered. This means that after a researcher had transcribed the interviewees' comments, the transcripts were organized, examined, arranged, and divided into sections. Re-listening to the interview's audio recording allows the researcher to validate and verify the interviewees' answers.

To fully comprehend the information and categorize the most recent, pertinent information, the researcher reviewed the transcripts numerous times. From the interview transcripts, supporting the categories was continuously gathered and organized anal and bets. The notions' recurrent patterns began to emerge as themes and codes. The data are analyzed by comparing the results to the literature after the themes were derived from the codes. As a

result, the researches compile all the findings in a descriptive manner. The researcher was able to gather the necessary information about the roles of NDLEA, causes, effects, and the contribution of family and community members in Uyo metropolis in reducing youth's drugs abuse.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study indicated that the causes of drugs abuse among youths include easy access to drugs in the country, peer group influence, despair, unemployment, failure of parental control over children, and drugs misuse. The result supports the assertion of Adegboro (2014), who opined that drug abuse is an issue that is getting worse every day, especially among youths. Drugs abuse has been acknowledged as a major destabilizing factor in national security dimensions in Nigeria. The rising trends in drugs abuse in Nigeria result in poverty, illiteracy, corruption, weak institutions/law enforcement and a lack of financing for (NDLEA), and other enforcement organizations, (Mboho, 2021).

The findings of the study indicate that the social consequence of drugs abuse among youths are decreased performance of youths at school and work place, reckless behaviour of youths at home, maltreatment of family members and youth criminality. This corresponds with the findings of Adelekan et al (2012) as cited in Aminu, et al, (2023) who found out that increased levels of insecurity in Nigeria are linked to drugs abuse. Yet, the most visible effect of illicit drug used in Nigeria is an inherent connection between it, crime and deviant behaviours. With the rise in the use of illicit drugs in the nation. several criminal activities, including armed robbery, kidnapping, ritual killing, rape, cybercrime, secret cult activities, and urban violence, have escalated (Willie; Mboho; and Oyosoro, 2022).

There are several studies that have linked the rise of drugs abuse to the increase of crime in Nigeria. One of such studies conducted by the National Bureau of Statistics in 2017 found that there is a significant correlation between drugs abuse and crime in Nigeria. The study revealed that drugs abuse is a major contributor to criminal activities such as armed robbery, kidnapping, and other forms of violence (Onipede, and Rasaq, 2018). In another study conducted by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) in 2019, reported that the use of illicit drugs is a major cause of crime in Nigeria. The study revealed that drugs abuse is prevalent among young people in Nigeria, and this has contributed to the increase in crime rates over the country (UNODC, 2019). Furthermore, a study conducted by Mboho, and Ataire (2018) on the prevalence and pattern of substance used among inmates of a Nigerian prison found that there is high prevalence of drug abuse among inmates in Nigerian prisons. The study revealed that drugs abuse is a major factor that contributes to the commission of crimes that lead to imprisonment.

On the financial consequence of drugs abuse, the study finds out that drugs abuse has significant financial consequences for the individual, their family, the health care system, and society as a whole. One of the major financial consequences of drugs abuse is the cost of treatment. Treatment for drug addiction can be expensive and may involve drug detoxification, counseling, behavioural therapy, medication, and rehabilitation programmes (Aminu, et al, 2023).. Secondly, drugs abuse can negatively impact employment status and income potential. Individuals struggling with drug addiction may experience difficulties in maintaining regular employment due to absenteeism, decreased productivity, and impaired

job performance. This can result in job loss, reduced income, and diminished career prospects. This is similar to the findings of Erah & Omatseye (2007) who confirm that calculating the financial costs of drugs abuse globally is difficult. Therefore, examining its effects allows us to get a better grasp of how drugs abuse affects the world.

On the other hand, drugs use and abuse, particularly among young peoples, has had detrimental consequences on states and societies economies, social cohesion, security, and stability. The findings of the study clearly reveal that health consequence of drugs abuse include early death, especially in people who have a low standard of life or consume few calories, which is common in underdeveloped nations and communities. Certain substances, such as cocaine and marijuana (cannabis), impair the immune system, harm reproductive organs, and raise the risk of birth problems. They also produce psychosis, mania, depersonalization, and general loss of purpose in life. This is similar to the findings of (Essien, (2010), as cited in Aminu, *et al*, 2023) who observes that considering their involvement in drugs abuse, the current health condition of Nigerian youths is depressing. Since 11 per cent of youth's population in Nigeria takes hard drugs, they suffer from drug use disorders.

CONCLUSION

The study on drugs abuse among youths in the Uyo metropolis represents a critical endeavor aimed at addressing a pressing public health and social issue. Through a comprehensive investigation into the prevalence, patterns, and socio-demographic correlates of drugs abuse, this study has contributed valuable insights that can inform targeted interventions, policies, and programs aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of substance misuse in the community. The findings of this study have shed light on the multifaceted nature of drugs abuse among youths in the metropolis, highlighting the prevalence of various types of substances abused, the socio-demographic characteristics of drug abusers, and the factors contributing to substance misuse. By identifying these key determinants, stakeholders can develop evidence based strategies to prevent initiation, reduce harm, and facilitate recovery among individuals affected by drugs abuse. Furthermore, this work has underscored the importance of adopting a holistic approach to addressing drug abuse, one that encompasses not only individual-level interventions but also community-wide initiatives aimed at promoting resilience, fostering protective factors, and enhancing access to support services. Collaboration among government agencies, non-governmental organizations, healthcare providers, educational institutions, law enforcement agencies, and community members will be essential for implementing effective prevention, treatment, and harm reduction efforts. As we move forward, it is imperative to prioritize ongoing monitoring and evaluation of interventions, as well as continued research to keep pace with evolving trends in drugs abuse and to identify emerging challenges and opportunities for intervention. By working together and leveraging interdisciplinary expertise, we can create a safer, healthier, and more supportive environment for youths in the Uyo metropolis and beyond, ultimately contributing to the well-being and prosperity of our communities. In closing, this research work represents a crucial step towards understanding and addressing the complex phenomenon of drugs abuse among youths, underscoring the importance of collective action and evidence-informed approaches in tackling this public health challenges.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the research work on drugs abuse among youths in the Uyo metropolis, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Design and implement comprehensive prevention programs targeting youths in schools, communities, and other relevant settings. These programs should focus on raising awareness about the risks of drugs abuse, building resilience, promoting positive coping strategies, and enhancing refusal skills.
2. Increase access to evidence-based treatment and support services for individuals struggling with drugs abuse and addiction. This includes expanding the availability of counseling, rehabilitation, and harm reduction services, as well as integrating substance abuse treatment into primary healthcare settings.
3. Strengthen enforcement efforts to disrupt the supply chain of illicit drugs and deter drug trafficking activities in the Uyo metropolis. This involves collaboration between law enforcement agencies, community leaders, and other stakeholders to identify and address drug-related crime hotspots.
4. Foster collaboration and coordination among government agencies, non-governmental organizations, healthcare providers, educational institutions, Law Enforcement Agencies, and community members to address drugs abuse comprehensively.
5. Parents and guardians should not neglect their responsibility to train members of their family irrespective of whether they are related by blood or by adoption.
6. Government should educate or enlightening parent on the effects of unmet needs like starvation (food), parental care and affection etc.
7. The government should enact measures on people that are selling drugs indiscriminately, and they should be supervising the target area at least monthly if possible and also check the activities of the victims of drugs abuse.

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